

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Demonstrator 2

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About AWARE2ALL

Facing to the challenge of future highly automated vehicles, where occupants can freely orient themselves to engage in non-driving activities. This new environment prompts questions about how car occupants will actually sit, what activities they will engage in, and how they will be informed through the HMI to keep them in the loop if necessary.

AWARE2ALL aims to pave the way towards Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) deployment in traffic, by effectively addressing the changes in road safety and changes in the interaction of different road users caused by the emergence of HAV through the development of innovative technologies along with the corresponding assessment tools and methodologies.

AWARE2ALL will develop safety and HMI systems that will be interrelated through achieving a holistic understanding of the scene to ensure safe operation of the HAV. AWARE2ALL proposes a common conceptual universal safety framework for considering Human Machine Interaction (HMI). The project will be built on the results of projects funded under H2020 and other R&D programmes addressing the identification of new safety-critical situations and the most likely positions and postures considering the expected HAV applications.

The main objective of AWARE2ALL is to address the new safety challenges posed by the introduction of HAVs in mixed road traffic, through the development of inclusive and innovative safety (passive and active) and HMI (interior and exterior) systems that will consider the variety of population and will objectively demonstrate relevant improvements in mixed traffic safety.

AWARE2ALL includes 16 partners from 6 EU Member States (ES, DE, GR, NL, FR and SE) and 2 associated countries (TR, CS) and it is complemented by the International Advisory Board (IAB) representing key stakeholders that covers the full research and industrial development automotive value chain, more specifically in the CCAM field.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
Acronyms and terms.....	8
1. Introduction	11
1.1. Purpose of the deliverable.....	11
1.2. Intended audience.....	11
2. Demonstrator 2	12
2.1. Physical System.....	12
2.2. Prediction of passenger body motion	13
2.2.1. Safe acceleration thresholds	13
2.2.2. Pre-Crash Trajectories.....	14
2.3. Fault-tolerant localization system.....	16
2.3.1. Vehicle localization system	16
2.3.2. Infrastructure localization system	22
2.3.3. Decision-making and vehicle control	28
3. Demonstrator 3	31
3.1. Physical systems	31
3.1.1. Main system.....	31
3.1.2. Secondary system.....	32
3.2. Active safety through risk estimation.....	34
3.2.1. Overview.....	34
3.2.2. Results.....	35
3.2.3. Conclusions.....	36
3.3. Transition of Control.....	36
3.3.1. Situational Awareness.....	37
3.3.2. Decision making for Transition of Control	37
3.4. Adaptive Co-Pilot.....	39
3.4.1. Shared control system	39
3.4.2. Shared control strategy.....	41
4. Conclusions	43
5. References	45

List of figures

Figure 1. Overview of the algorithms developed for Demonstrator 2	12
Figure 2. Shuttle platform from PiX, external and inner view	12
Figure 3. Acceleration pulse.....	14
Figure 4. Different simulation setups for the Madymo Active Human Model	14
Figure 5 Generated trajectories in the x-y-coordinate space.....	15
Figure 6. Robobus's CHC NAV-610 GNSS-INS.....	16
Figure 7. GNSS-INS, in orange, displayed in Autoware.....	17
Figure 8. KISS-ICP odometry, in green, vs GNSS-INS, in orange, displayed in Autoware.....	18
Figure 9. Schematic of the fault tolerant localization	19
Figure 10. Fault tolerant localization. Position through time with GNSS, LiDAR Odometry and LiDAR Map (NDT)	20
Figure 11. Fault tolerant localization. Yaw angle over time with GNSS, LiDAR Odometry and LiDAR Map (NDT)	20
Figure 12. Fault tolerant localization. Position through time with LiDAR Odometry and LiDAR Map (NDT).....	21
Figure 13. Fault tolerant localization. Yaw angle over time with LiDAR Odometry and LiDAR Map (NDT).....	21
Figure 14: Infrastructure prototype.....	22
Figure 15: Hesai AT128.....	23
Figure 16: Unicore UM982	23
Figure 17: Stereolabs ZED X.....	24
Figure 18: Nvidia Jetson Orin 64 GB.....	24
Figure 19: infrastructure-shuttle synchronisation.....	25
Figure 20. Commsignia devices: RSU ITS-RS4 (left) and OBU ITS-OB4 (right)	26
Figure 21. General Structure of a CPM	27
Figure 22. Capture of CPM sending from the infrastructure via RSU, and its reception in the Shuttle through the OBU.....	27
Figure 23. RSU in the experimental test track.....	28
Figure 24 PCD map with the lanelet map.....	29
Figure 25: Shuttle in the test track with the Autoware HMI	30
Figure 26. Hybrid driving simulator.....	32
Figure 27. Dynamic driving simulator and the active pedal.....	33
Figure 28. Haptic pedals for vehicle throttle and brake, HW controller box and configuration GUI.....	33

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 29. Architecture of the planner.	35
Figure 30: Overtaking scenario with varying uncertainty (note that the time is only depicted for the high uncertainty case for visibility).....	36
Figure 31. Interconnection of algorithms for Transition of Control in Demonstrator 3	37
Figure 32. Dockerized solution for shared control system	39
Figure 33. Graphic user interface for adjusting the NMPC weight and plotter to debug the MPC controller.....	40
Figure 34. Integration of Actuators, Shared Control and CARLA modules using dockers and ROS2.....	41
Figure 35. Real data printing when MPC is operative for nodes simulator, MPC and planner.	41

List of tables

Table 1. Shuttle sensors and equipment	13
Table 2. Infrastructure sensors.....	13
Table 3. CHC NAV-610 Performance Specifications.....	17
Table 4: MPC parameters for the lateral controller.	29
Table 5: PID parameters for the longitudinal controller.	29

Executive Summary

This document is to describe D2.2, the Active Safety Demonstrators, which is of deliverable type DEMO. As such it reports what has been developed and implemented in the demonstrators 2 and 3 to improve current active safety systems: from perception, through interpretation and planning to action. These are mainly the results of the research topics included in task 2.2 of the AWARE2ALL project. Hence, not all algorithms that will be implemented and evaluated in Demonstrator 3 are documented here. The results of WP3 Occupant Monitoring and iHMI solutions are described in the WP3 deliverables: D3.1 – Occupant state and behaviour analysis and development, D3.2 – In-cabin integration of OMS technologies and components (OMS: Occupant Monitoring Systems), and D3.3 – Cognitive empathic HMI Design and Implementation (HMI: Human Machine Interface).

For task 2.2 the following is thus reported here:

Demonstrator 2:

- The Robobus from PiX¹, is an autonomous shuttle platform designed to operate without a human driver, utilizing sensors, cameras and AI technology to navigate roads and transport passengers safely. Additionally, to support the localization system, a LiDAR and algorithms for roadside detection of the shuttle were setup and programmed as well as I2V communication from the roadside to the shuttle.
- Prediction of passenger body motion that is based on acceleration values resulting from pre-crash simulations. Using MADYMO, different human models (active and passive), placed in various standing poses (facing forward and facing sideways) and configurations (two hands on the vehicle grab handle, one or none) and sitting positions rearwards and forward facing have been evaluated to find limiting accelerations for safe manoeuvring.
- The result of the passenger body motion is input for the design of pre-crash trajectories. An algorithm has been designed to take the limiting accelerations into account for an optimal upcoming pre-crash scenario.
- Improved operational reliability through deployment strategies for fault-tolerant strategies in case of system positioning sensor failure including fail-operational functionalities, and emergency situations, such as AEB, evasive manoeuvring or safe/comfortable stops. Following scenarios have been implemented:
 - o degradation of the GNSS signal: an algorithm using I2V localisation information is designed as a fault-tolerant strategy.
 - o when additionally to the GNSS degradation also the LiDAR-based positioning algorithm fails then an algorithm based on I2V localisation is activated.
- Decision making and control of the shuttle: these algorithms control the motion of the shuttle either in normal operation or in one of the pre-crash scenarios connected to this demonstrator.

Demonstrator 3:

¹ PiX shuttles: <https://www.pixmoving.com/>

D2.2 – Active Safety System

- The main physical system is the hybrid driving simulator from partner SYSX. It is based on a physical cockpit and a virtual environment to run the (human factors) experiments.
- Risk field estimation and safety relevant trajectory adaptation and control modules are researched and applied to increase the lateral acceleration range for the evasive manoeuvre including the acceptance of lane change manoeuvre.
- An algorithm has been designed to estimate the readiness of the driver to resume control after automated driving. This algorithm, referred to as Decision Making, takes as input the results of specific algorithms designed in WP3, such as Situation Awareness estimation, hands on/off detection, driver health, cognitive workload, and criticality of the situation. The result of the Decision Making algorithm is used to shape the transition of control from automated driving to manual driving.
- Adaptive support for drivers, depending on the driving context, such as driver state (e.g. from the Decision Making algorithm) or risk estimation, by means of steering system and haptic pedals. This comprises a haptic shared control algorithm, supported by a drive-by-wire setup with a haptic steering wheel and haptic accelerator pedal. All parts were implemented in a driving simulator of partner TEC (parallel part of Demonstrator 3).

Acronyms and terms

Acronym	Term
AD	Autonomous Driving
AEB	Autonomous Emergency Braking
AHM	Active Human Model
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CPM	Collective Perception Message
ECG	Electroencephalography
EEG	Electrocardiography
EKF	Extended Kalman Filter
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
I2V	Infrastructure to Vehicle [communication]
GLONASS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HAV	Highly Automated Vehicle
iHMI	internal HMI
HMI	Human Machine Interface
INS	Inertial Navigation System
ITS	Intelligent Transport System

D2.2 – Active Safety System

KISS-ICP	Keep It Simple Stupid - Iterative Closest Point
LCD	Liquid-Crystal Display
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
MAC	Medium Access Control
MPC	Model Predictive Controller
NDT	Normal Distributions Transform
NMPC	Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
NVH	Noise, Vibration, and Harshness
OBU	OnBoard Unit
OMS	Occupant Monitoring Systems
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PCD	Point Cloud Data
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative [control]
QP	Quadratic Programming
ROS2	Robot Operating System 2
RSU	RoadSide Unit
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
SLAM	Simultaneous localization and mapping
SMPC	Stochastic Model Predictive Control
USB	Universal Serial Bus
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
V2X	Communication from/to a vehicle to/from any other entity

D2.2 – Active Safety System

VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WAVE	Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of this document is to relate what has been implemented in the Demonstrators 2 and 3 to improve current active safety systems: from perception, through interpretation and planning to action. These are mainly the results of the research topics included in task 2.2 of the AWARE2ALL project. Hence, not all algorithms that will be implemented and evaluated in Demonstrator 3 are documented here. The results of WP3 Occupant Monitoring and iHMI solutions are described in the WP3 deliverables: D3.1 (Muttersbach & Löw, 2024), D3.2 (Cañas, 2025 (in progress)), and D3.3 (Amokrane-Ferka, 2025 (in progress)). In consequence, this deliverable reports the results of the research topics on active safety systems carried out in task 2.2, which are included in Demonstrators 2 and 3, whose validation reports will be produced at the end of the project in WP5 deliverables.

For task 2.2 following is reported:

Demonstrator 2:

- Prediction of passenger body motion that is based on acceleration values resulting from pre-crash simulations. The result of the passenger body motion is input to the strategy to prepare the passengers for the upcoming motion of the shuttle: HMI and active restraint systems. Moreover, in this task, it is input to the optimisation algorithm that finds the best trajectory in case of an imminent collision.
- Improved operational reliability through deployment strategies for fallback/fault-tolerant strategies in case of system positioning sensors failure including fail-operational functionalities, and emergency situations, such as AEB, evasive manoeuvring or safe/comfortable stops. The system will additionally exploit V2X interconnection with infrastructure to improve localization accuracy.

Demonstrator 3:

- Increase the lateral acceleration range for the evasive manoeuvre including the acceptance of lane change manoeuvre. To realise this, risk field estimation and the safety relevant trajectory adaptation and control modules are researched and applied.
- Different transition of control strategies depending on the anticipated driver state at takeover (request). This may include different timing of the take-over request, trajectories driven after the take-over request, and, in this task, different types of driver support just after the actual take over. Pre-warning for correct situational awareness will be considered as well.
- Adaptive support for drivers, depending on the driving context, such as driver state or risk estimation, by means of steering system and haptic pedals.

1.2. Intended audience

The information in this deliverable is mainly meant for two groups of audience. Firstly, there is the project internal audience: mainly for WP5, to anticipate on the required testing. Secondly, there is the project external audience: monitor what has been researched and implemented in AWARE2ALL, task 2.2.

2. Demonstrator 2

This chapter describes the Demonstrator, an autonomous shuttle, in section 2.1. Sections 2.2 and 2.3 describe the added hardware and associated algorithms needed for the AWARE2ALL project.

Figure 1 gives an overview of the developed algorithms for Demonstrator 2.

Figure 1. Overview of the algorithms developed for Demonstrator 2

Section 2.2.1 discusses the (Standing) occupant motion simulation that generates the safe acceleration thresholds. Section 2.2.2 presents the research performed on Optimal evasive manoeuvring and Pre-crash manoeuvres.

Section 2.3.1 presents the localisation system of the vehicle and the fallback strategies using these systems. Section 2.3.2 adds the localisation system from the infrastructure side to the fall back strategies. Finally, section 2.3.3 combines both information of the infrastructure, internal camera’s and of the pre-crash manoeuvres of section 2.2 to decide on the optimal control of the shuttle.

2.1. Physical System

The Robobus from PiX², is an autonomous shuttle platform designed to operate without a human driver, utilizing sensors, cameras and AI technology to navigate roads and transport passengers safely. The shuttle is equipped with two seats (front-view and rear-view) with space for three persons each, and enough space in the middle for two standing passengers, as shown in Figure 2. It also comes with speakers inside the vehicle and a large screen in the middle that can be used as an HMI to communicate with the passengers.

Figure 2. Shuttle platform from PiX, external and inner view

² PiX shuttles: <https://www.pixmoving.com/>

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Table 1 shows the different sensors and devices used by the shuttle and its various modules (navigation, perception, communication, and control).

Table 1. Shuttle sensors and equipment

Module	Item	Description
Navigation	GNSS with integrated IMU	CGI-610
External perception	LiDAR	Ouster 32-OS1
Internal perception	2 USB Cameras	In front each bench seats
Network	Switch	-
	Router	-
Control unit	Industrial PC	Karbon 700 - OnLogic
I2V	1 On-board unit	Commsignia

Table 2 shows the devices installed in infrastructure for the detection of the shuttle and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) in the zone to be communicated to the shuttle through Infrastructure to Vehicle (I2V) communication technology.

Table 2. Infrastructure sensors

Module	Item	Description
I2V	1 Road-side unit	Commsignia
LiDAR	1 in the bus stop	Hesai AT128
Camera	1 in the bus stop	Zed X
GNSS	1 in the bus stop	-

2.2. Prediction of passenger body motion

For the prediction of the occupant's motion during active safety evasive manoeuvres, the Madymo (TASS International Software and Services, Helmond, the Netherlands.) simulation environment was used. The validated Madymo Active Human Model (AHM) was exposed in different acceleration pulses and directions and poses. The acceleration pulses were applied to a sled representing the vehicle floor. Thresholds for safe accelerations were identified based on the criterion of the AHM maintaining balance. These thresholds used as a basis for safe evasive manoeuvres.

2.2.1. Safe acceleration thresholds

The AHM model was used for the simulation of occupant balance maintenance in different poses and directions. Pre-simulations of the AHM were performed in order to stabilize the model in the

D2.2 – Active Safety System

initial pose. The simulation duration was 1.5 s. The acceleration pulses were incremental from 1 m/s^2 – 10 m/s^2 with a step of 0.5 m/s^2 . The acceleration pulse shape had a ramp-up time of 0.2 s and from there remained constant until 1.5 s (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Acceleration pulse

The acceleration was in four directions (longitudinal forward, backwards and lateral left and right relative to the vehicle motion). The AHM poses were in four different setups as presented in Figure 4. Standing poses with different grip configurations (different height of handle grip and standing without grip) and sitting poses (with and without seatbelt). The AHM was used mainly unmodified while the grip parameters used were according to the literature and the Madymo AHM application guidelines. The maximum acceleration in which the AHM maintained their balance was considered as the threshold. While a second, lower, value for comfortable acceleration was considered for the criterion that the head displacement is less than 20 cm.

Figure 4. Different simulation setups for the Madymo Active Human Model

2.2.2. Pre-Crash Trajectories

To identify the most critical and relevant pre-crash pulses for the passengers, we performed a case study where we analysed the impact of certain active safety manoeuvres on the crash severity of the passengers. Following this approach, we created trajectories out of this case study with the simulation tool IPG CarMaker and used the resulting trajectories to perform a detailed impact analysis in Madymo. The physical specifications of Demonstrator 2 have therefore been transferred into CarMaker to obtain a realistic system behaviour. We are covering nearly all possible pre-crash trajectories and subsequent pre-crash pulses by a combined lateral and longitudinal variation of the

D2.2 – Active Safety System

corresponding actuators for steering and braking. Note that throttle is typically not used for evasive manoeuvring. Based on (Becker, Östling, Lozano, Klein, & Weihmayr, 2022) we assume that we can rebuild a possible trajectory with a combination of the following manoeuvres:

- Driving straight without braking
- Driving straight with braking
- Driving a one-sided curve without braking
- Driving a one-sided curve with braking
- Driving an S-curve without braking
- Driving an S-curve with braking

Driving a straight manoeuvre means to keep the steering angle at 0° , driving a one-sided curve means to adjust and change the steering angle increasingly towards the left or right end, and the S-curve includes frequent changes in the steering angle both positive and negative angles. Further, we include the longitudinal control by braking. Typically, we use 100% of the available braking force during an evasive manoeuvre, which means a maximum deceleration of -4.1 m/s^2 for Demonstrator 2. Considering its maximum driving velocity of 30 km/h and the maximum steering angle of 29° , we do not see any conflicts or limitations related to the maximum friction circle and tyres respectively. All simulated trajectories start with a velocity of 30 km/h. We combine different steering angles and manoeuvres with our so-called action points. Each simulation consists of six seconds straight driving with 30 km/h for initialisation purposes followed by 4 action points at a discrete time difference of 0.5 s and an additional second after the last action point. With the initialisation time removed, we end up with a total simulation time of 2.5 s for each trajectory. The simulation itself covers multiple relevant vehicle states for the subsequent analysis. Each action point has the ability to change longitudinal and lateral control at once. In terms of longitudinal control, we apply the full braking. Once one action point triggers the braking, all remaining action points are forced to keep the full braking until the standstill of the vehicle. The steering angle has 5 different modes of operation [-29° ; $-17,4^\circ$; $-5,8^\circ$; 0° ; $5,8^\circ$; $17,4^\circ$; 29°]. Minor manoeuvres with a lower steering angle might not result in the most severe pre-crash pulses for seated passengers but might be already harmful to standing passengers. All 3125 simulated trajectories are plotted in the figure below which shows the relevant 2.5 s for the vehicle's x- and y-movement in global coordinates.

Figure 5 Generated trajectories in the x-y-coordinate space.

2.3. Fault-tolerant localization system

Fault-tolerant functionalities are designed to continue functioning safely even if one or more components or subsystems fail. The goal is to ensure that the vehicle can maintain a basic level of operation or safely come to a stop in the event of a failure, reducing the risk of accidents or disruptions.

In the context of autonomous vehicles, it implies that even if certain sensors, processors, or other critical components experience a malfunction, the vehicle can still operate in a safe manner, possibly with degraded functionality. This is crucial for ensuring the safety and reliability of autonomous vehicles, as any failure in critical systems could have serious consequences. In this context, the implementation of fault-tolerant localization strategies becomes crucial for addressing system failures and maintaining safe operations. This is especially relevant for vehicles, particularly regarding the localization functionality.

2.3.1. Vehicle localization system

The vehicle localization system will receive inputs from two main sources: 1) A GNSS-INS for satellite-based positioning, 2) Lidar-based positioning, both from a map-based approach using an NDT algorithm and a LiDAR-odometry strategy. The three localization inputs will go through an EKF.

GNSS-INS

The GNSS-INS used in the PIX Robobus is a CHC-NAV 610 double-antenna device. It includes an inertial navigation system (INS) for precise localization and speed estimation. This INS is installed on the Robobus's rear axle. A scheme of this GNSS-INS and its double-antenna installation in the Robobus is shown in **Figure 6**, as well as its performance specifications in **Table 3**.

Figure 6. Robobus's CHC NAV-610 GNSS-INS

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Table 3. CHC NAV-610 Performance Specifications

Outage duration	Positioning mode	Position accuracy – RMS (m)		Velocity accuracy – RMS (m/s)	
		Horizontal	Vertical	Horizontal	Vertical
0 s	RTK-Float	0.30	0.15	0.15	0.05
10 s	RTK-Fix	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02

We integrated this GNSS device into the Autoware environment, obtaining a global positioning in UTM coordinates, including position and orientation. Moreover, we separated the INS combination with the GNSS positioning for more precise adjustment in the fault-tolerant system afterwards. Thus, the overall output of the GNSS-INS device is the following:

- Pose with covariance. A message containing the global positioning in UTM coordinates, orientation in quaternion-based format, and covariances of position and orientation.
- Velocity stamped. A message containing the current linear and angular velocities given by the INS device.

Figure 7. GNSS-INS, in orange, displayed in Autoware

LiDAR Localization

For LiDAR localization, the Robobus has 4 Ouster-OS1 32 beams installed, which are fused through Autoware's point cloud preprocessor module.

- **LiDAR Odometry.** For the LiDAR Odometry estimation, we use KISS-ICP, which stands for "Keep It Simple Stupid - Iterative Closest Point". It is a simplified version of the widely used ICP (Iterative Closest Point) algorithm, which is used for aligning two sets of 3D points in a common coordinate system. The KISS-ICP algorithm simplifies the traditional ICP method by reducing computational complexity and improving its efficiency. In each iteration, KISS-ICP finds the closest points between the two consecutive point clouds. Unlike traditional ICP, KISS-ICP limits the search for the closest points to a simplified approach, which reduces the number of calculations needed. KISS-ICP's integration in Autoware was done by georeferencing its measurements to the first accurate position of the GNSS-INS device.
- **Map-based LiDAR Localization.** For the Map-based LiDAR localization, we use NDT (Normal Distributions Transform), which is a more sophisticated method for point cloud registration

D2.2 – Active Safety System

and localization compared to KISS-ICP. It is particularly effective in dealing with noisy or incomplete data, which is common in real-world environments. The basic idea of NDT is to model the environment using probabilistic distributions rather than just raw point clouds, allowing for more robust and accurate alignment. NDT's integration in Autoware is straight forward, since this AD stack already uses it as its localization system, allowing to use GNSS-INS measurements to set up (and reset) the initial pose for this method.

Figure 8. KISS-ICP odometry, in green, vs GNSS-INS, in orange, displayed in Autoware

Fault-tolerant localization system

In the case of this Demonstrator a fault tolerant strategy to account for failures in the positioning system has been designed. The positioning system, constituted by GNSS, a LiDAR odometry algorithm (without map), and a map-based LiDAR localization is enhanced with an additional localization source based on communication with infrastructure. The fault tolerant strategy will depend on the localization sources available at the time.

When the vehicle is moving and all localization sources are working correctly, an EKF-based fusion of GNSS + LiDAR Odometry + map-based LiDAR localization + I2V-localization is to be performed. The main difficulty of this strategy is the time delay management, as each localization source provides the solution with different delays.

The GNSS has, when using differential corrections, a very accurate performance, but is subject to undesired external effects that decrease the accuracy, such as signal disruptions, the multipath effect or even signal jamming. Therefore, it cannot be employed as the only localization source. The map-based LiDAR localization has also a general good performance, but it depends on the validity of the pre-recorded point cloud map, which can become outdated. Besides, it suffers with high angular velocities. On the other hand, the LiDAR odometry does not depend on a pre-recorded point cloud map, but has a reduced accuracy and drifts over time, accumulating error. Finally, the I2V-based localization has a good accuracy, but suffers from time delays in the communication process.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 9. Schematic of the fault tolerant localization

In the first scenario, the shuttle suffers a degradation of the GNSS signal. A LiDAR-only-based localization is not precise enough to provide accurate manoeuvring at the shuttle stop. Consequently, the I2V-localization will be used in an EKF to improve the accuracy and to correct the drift accumulated by the SLAM algorithm. Besides that, further techniques of localization based on object detection are being explored.

In the second scenario, both LiDAR-based algorithms also suffer a failure. This situation leads to the I2V-localization as the main exteroceptive positioning source, being complemented by model-based dead reckoning. Again, further techniques of localization based on object detection are being explored.

The next figures show the Fault tolerant localization system with the GNSS, the LiDAR Odometry and the map-based LiDAR localization. Figure 10 shows the vehicle position over time, while Figure 11 shows the yaw angle estimation. As it can be seen, the GNSS and the map-based LiDAR localization are the localization sources that have the biggest effect on the final output, but they are also the most accurate.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 10. Fault tolerant localization. Position through time with GNSS, LiDAR Odometry and LiDAR Map (NDT)

Figure 11. Fault tolerant localization. Yaw angle over time with GNSS, LiDAR Odometry and LiDAR Map (NDT)

Next, the performance is examined using only the LiDAR-based localization methods. Figure 12 shows the position over time, while Figure 13 shows the yaw angle. Again, the most accurate localization source has more weight in the final output.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 12. Fault tolerant localization. Position through time with LiDAR Odometry and LiDAR Map (NDT)

Figure 13. Fault tolerant localization. Yaw angle over time with LiDAR Odometry and LiDAR Map (NDT)

D2.2 – Active Safety System

2.3.2. Infrastructure localization system

The infrastructure will be in the shuttle stop, where passengers get in and out. A LiDAR sensor is on the top of the station, monitoring the shuttle that is approaching. We will train a deep learning model based on LiDAR to accurately detect and locate the shuttle from the infrastructure. The location of the shuttle needs to be sent to the shuttle to support positioning using I2V communications to help the Fault-tolerant localization system with another localization source.

Figure 14: Infrastructure prototype

In addition, the infrastructure must detect potential hazards entering the road. In particular, this implementation must take into account unexpected pedestrians. It will be based on a camera that can accurately detect pedestrians and locate them on the map to help the shuttle make an evasive manoeuvre. The camera complements the LiDAR by accurately detecting pedestrians, as their small sizes make them difficult to detect using point cloud data. The shuttle's position and pedestrian location information is sent to the shuttle via I2V communication, enabling it to perform a precise manoeuvre in the event of a localisation system failure.

The infrastructure is made up of various sensors and computing units, each with its own purpose. The following section explains the contribution and purpose of each component, the complete infrastructure can be seen on Figure 14.

First, we tested several LiDARs to select the best one for our proposal. At the beginning of the project, we used an Ouster OS-1 with 32 layers. However, we lost half of the points because we could not use the 360 degrees on an infrastructure setup. So, we switched to a solid-state LiDAR, which gives us a denser point cloud at the front. We chose a Hesai AT128, which produces 1,536,000 points/s with a field of view of $120^\circ \times 25.4^\circ$. In contrast, the Ouster produces 655,360 points/s, which is less than half the points of the Hesai, without considering the points lost due to the field of view.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 15: Hesai AT128

The proposed infrastructure is a mobile prototype, so we need to be able to place it in a different location each time without the need for calibration. To achieve this, we have installed a dual-antenna GNSS with RTK corrections, which will provide an accurate position and orientation of the infrastructure. This will allow us to move the entire system for each survey or test and have our setup calibrated. The GNSS used is a low-cost device commonly used in drones, because we don't need the Inertial Motion Unit, which is the expensive component of a high-end GNSS, we can use it perfectly. The device employed is the Unicore UM982, which can be seen in Figure 16. Both antennas have been positioned with a meter of distance between them, which gives a good enough heading estimation.

Figure 16: Unicore UM982

For the camera, we want a camera that allows us to get accurate 3D object detection, as this is a big problem with monocular cameras, and we could not develop new software for this application. We chose a stereo camera (Figure 17) that provides in-depth information, which solves the 2D problem and gives us a 3D estimate of the detected objects. The 3D objects can be transformed into a global frame and sent to the shuttle, which uses this information to avoid collisions.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 17: Stereolabs ZED X

To process all the data generated by the sensors, we have a 64GB Nvidia Jetson Orin-based central processing unit (Figure 18). This is an embedded computer from Nvidia that enables GPU computing using only 60 W of power. However, we had a problem integrating the GNSS because one of the USB cables was not recognized by the Jetson because it required a modification to the Nvidia kernel. To overcome this, we added a Raspberry Pi 4 to handle the GNSS.

Figure 18: Nvidia Jetson Orin 64 GB

To collect the data, we developed an automatic synchronization tool that saved us from having to label all the data manually. This was very useful because one of the main problems with deep learning is that it requires a lot of human resources to collect the data. With this tool, however, we are able to collect data from our vehicles without any manual interaction. To achieve this milestone, we synchronized the clocks of the Nvidia Jetson Orin and the industrial PC on the shuttle. We did this using the GNSS clock, which is an external synchronized clock. In addition, because the infrastructure is accurately positioned, we can do the transformation from the shuttle and the infrastructure to have both data in the same frame. This allows us to fuse the two pieces of information because we have the synchronized time and the spatial information in the same frame.

Figure 19 shows the shuttle placed over the point cloud thanks to the synchronization of both systems for automatic labelling. The LiDAR is able to see the entire test track, allowing the shuttle to be detected throughout the manoeuvre.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 19: infrastructure-shuttle synchronisation

I2V communication

This stage allows to send and receive data, between the infrastructure and the vehicle (I2V, Vehicle to Infrastructure and vice versa) for optimal and safe manoeuvre management. The information obtained by these systems can be processed in the decision stage for planning trajectories, to increase their safety and reliability.

The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), in collaboration with other international centres, has defined the Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE) standard. The standard describes the specifications in the communication packages according to the different scenarios that may occur in automated driving.

The IEEE 802.11p standard defines the physical and the medium access layer (Medium Access Control, MAC) following the OSI model (Open Systems Interconnection). It includes short-range communications for communications devices, such as RoadSide Units (RSU) and On-Board Units (OBU), including the IPv6 protocol. Currently, the IEEE 802.11p standard constitutes one of the protocols under which vehicular networks are supported, such as ETSI ITS G5 in Europe. This protocol defines the communication requirements, procedures, and algorithms at the physical and MAC layer level necessary to transfer vehicular information on highly variable channels in time.

Following the ETSI ITS G5, communications with the Shuttle will be carried out through a Commsignia ITS-OB4 collocated in the Robobus, and a Commsignia ITS-RS4 installed in the infrastructure (see Figure 20). The OBU has a dual 5.9 GHz antenna with GPS/GLONASS, Wifi, and WiMax capabilities.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 20. Commsignia devices: RSU ITS-RS4 (left) and OBU ITS-OB4 (right)

Among the messages for vehicular communication, mainly the Collective Perception Messages (CPM) will be used. The exchange of these messages enhances situational awareness through collaborative perception, enabling vehicles to extend their sensing capabilities beyond their sensor limitations. This shared information network facilitates comprehensive detection and monitoring of objects, vehicles, and infrastructure elements across various environmental conditions, proximate and distant, including occluded areas, curved roadways, and intersections. Such enhanced perceptual capabilities significantly contribute to the system's overall effectiveness in performing autonomous manoeuvres reliably and safely.

The CPMs are designed to facilitate collective perception in vehicular environments. These messages allow vehicles and road units to share information about objects detected in their environment, such as other vehicles, pedestrians, bicycles, or obstacles. Their implementation is specified in the ETSI TS 103 324 standard (ETSI TS 103 324 Intelligent Transport System (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Collective Perception Service; Release 2), which defines the technical and structural aspects necessary for their operation in the context of the ITS.

The structure of CPM messages follows a modular and hierarchical design, as shown in Figure 21. The header contains basic information about the message, such as the sender identifier, the location of the ITS node, the time of issue, and other relevant data to ensure synchronization and efficient use of network resources.

The payload consists of two components: the management container, which provides basic information necessary to process the other information in the CPM, and the second component consists of the type identifier of the container and the container's data.

In this project, the container shared is the Perceived Object Container (highlighted in Figure 21). It provides information about objects that have been perceived through the sensory capabilities of the infrastructure.

Finally, Figure 23 illustrates the placement of the RSU within the experimental test track utilized for Demonstrator 2 development.

Figure 23. RSU in the experimental test track

2.3.3. Decision-making and vehicle control

The decision module receives the information from the infrastructure and from the camera-based passenger monitoring system installed inside the shuttle. The goal of the evasive manoeuvre is to (1) avoid an accident with the VRU and (2) avoid excessive acceleration that affects the passengers inside the vehicle.

The risk of the manoeuvre concerning the passengers will be based on the simulation's studies performed by CETH and THI as described in Section 2.2.

The Autoware project serves as the base autonomous driving (AD) framework for planning and control, providing a comprehensive AD stack with various integrated modules. Its modular architecture enables developers to customize and replace components, facilitating the integration of additional features.

For vehicle control, Autoware implements two main techniques: Model Predictive Control (MPC) for lateral control and Proportional, Integral, Derivative (PID) control for longitudinal control.

Specifically, it employs linear model predictive control for precise path tracking. The MPC utilizes a vehicle model to simulate the trajectory resulting from control commands. The control command optimization is formulated as a Quadratic Program (QP) using a kinematic bicycle model. For the Shuttle, the MPC parameters are presented in Table 4:

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Table 4: MPC parameters for the lateral controller.

Variable	Value
Prediction Horizon step	100
Prediction Horizon delta time	0.1
Weight lateral error	6.0
Weight heading error	1.5

The longitudinal control calculates target acceleration to achieve desired velocities at each point along the trajectory using feed-forward/feed-back control. It incorporates slope force correction to account for road gradients and includes delay compensation. The system assumes the calculated target acceleration will be properly executed by the vehicle interface. The parameters for the PID control are shown in Table 5:

Table 5: PID parameters for the longitudinal controller.

Variable	Value
Kp	5.0
Ki	0.0
Kd	0.1

Testing of vehicle components takes place at the Tecnia test track—a circuit featuring road segments 80 m in length and 15 m in width. Both a PCD map and a lanelet map have been created for vehicle navigation. The PCD map supports SLAM functionality, while the lanelet map provides lane information in global coordinates. Both representations are shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24 PCD map with the lanelet map.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Autoware features an interactive Human Machine Interface (HMI) through Rviz, displaying the vehicle trajectory, obstacles, and vehicle position, along with necessary driving commands. Figure 25 shows the HMI view alongside the vehicle on the test track.

Figure 25: Shuttle in the test track with the Autoware HMI

3. Demonstrator 3

The technologies implemented in Demonstrator 3 are the result of 2 work packages. Firstly, WP3 develops different algorithms to track the state of the occupant(s) and ways to interact with them (internal HMI, iHMI).

Secondly, WP2 develops algorithms for active safety: Transition of Control, a larger acceleration range for evasive manoeuvring and adaptive driver support.

This chapter describes Demonstrator 3 as used in the project. There is one main system: the driving simulator of partner SystemX (see section 3.1.1) and a smaller driving simulator of partner Tecnalía (see section 3.1.2). After the description of the physical systems, the implemented technologies as developed in task 2.2 of the project are described:

- Section 3.2 discusses Active safety through risk estimation,
- Section 3.3 describes the algorithms connected to Transition of Control:
 - o Situation Awareness,
 - o Decision Making for Transition of Control,
- Section 3.4 describes the adaptive Co-pilot for shared control between the driver and the automated vehicle.

3.1. Physical systems

The physical systems used for Demonstrator 3 consist of two systems: the main system is the driving simulator of SystemX, an additional system is the driving simulator of Tecnalía. Both systems are described in the next subsections.

3.1.1. Main system

The physical system is the hybrid driving simulator from SystemX. It is based on a physical cockpit and a virtual environment to run the (human factors) experiments (see **Figure 26**). The physical cockpit is composed of a 180° hemispheric screen and a test vehicle equipped with different actuators and sensors. It allows multimodal HMI configurations to be tested. To do so, the cockpit is equipped with screens (cluster, central display, HUD, and mirrors), LEDs (side windows, windshield, steering wheel), speakers (cockpit + headrest), and seat actuators. Haptic feedback in the steering wheel can also be controlled using a sensodrive motor.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 26. Hybrid driving simulator

Several data can be collected and processed for evaluation: physiological data (EEG, ECG), driver monitoring data (gaze tracking, head position), driver-HAV interaction data (seat occupancy, interaction with steering wheel and pedal), sensor data (vehicle cameras, LiDAR sensors, radar sensors) and driving data (speed, position in lane, longitudinal & lateral accelerations, etc.).

The simulator is equipped with 4 cameras: 3 cameras recording the actions on the pedals, the driver from its right rear and right front and a free camera that can be mounted inside or outside the vehicle.

The cockpit is designed to provide drivers with a driving experience as immersive and ecological as possible. The simulation environment is provided by SCANeR and integrated in a platform that provides tools and methodology to specify simulation scenarios, run experiments, gather, and analyse data.

3.1.2. Secondary system

The additional system for Demonstrator 3 consists of a dynamic driving simulator from Tecnelia. The driver-oriented cockpit is equipped with three 32-inch LCD screens, an 18 Nm torque steering wheel, and adjustable passive pedals (gas and brake). The touch display and stereo audio system contribute to the overall authenticity of the simulation.

The simulator includes a 5 degrees of freedom platform enabling roll, pitch, yaw, heave, and surge. This platform is equipped with a bass shaker to reproduce realistic noises, vibrations, and a harshness (NVH) environment, providing a more engaging and lifelike experience.

For the monitoring of the driver's engagement, Pupil Labs eye tracking glasses are available to monitor the gaze of the driver.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 27. Dynamic driving simulator and the active pedal

The simulation environment is powered by CARLA, a sophisticated simulation environment known for its detailed and realistic rendering. The integration of all control and peripheral systems is efficiently managed through ROS2 (Robot Operating System 2), ensuring seamless communication and coordination among different components.

In an upgrade of the simulator, haptic actuators from Sensodrive were integrated. In the first place, a force-feedback steering wheel with faster response time (1 ms) than the previous one, and with a maximum torque of 15 Nm. In the second place, a set of active haptic pedals (see Figure 28) were integrated for both throttle and brake. With this new configuration, the shared control algorithms can be integrated for both longitudinal and lateral control of the vehicle.

Figure 28. Haptic pedals for vehicle throttle and brake, HW controller box and configuration GUI.

3.2. Active safety through risk estimation

3.2.1. Overview

The active safety module plans and controls safe trajectories when detecting a critical situation. To ensure safety, a risk metric representing the expected severity of a collision is integrated. The risk measure uses the prediction of other road users and a potential ego vehicle trajectory to estimate the risk. The total risk along a trajectory is then calculated and serves as an optimization criterion within a model predictive controller (MPC). While the MPC minimizes the risk along a trajectory, it balances it with path-following performance. A path is a reference curve leading to a desired goal destination along a reference speed. Thus, balancing risk with path-following performance generates the ego vehicle's behaviour. The architecture of the planner is depicted in **Figure 29**. Here, the optimization variables are the input sequences to a vehicle model, representing the ego vehicle dynamics. Further, with the reference path and velocity, a timing law determines the progress along the path and, therefore, is used to calculate the error from the references. Besides the reference convergence, the planner calculates the risk along the motion plan by using uncertain pedestrian predictions. Here, not only the risk of colliding with other road users is considered, but also the risk of colliding with infrastructure. Such is represented by a potential field, of which a large potential indicates an area of significant collision severity. As such, the potential field represents the risk of colliding with static targets, while the uncertain predictions consider all dynamic targets. Lastly, the planner also considers general constraints in the state and input space. The result is an input sequence for a planning horizon, i.e., steering and acceleration signals. The optimization problem is solved recursively in a moving horizon fashion; hence, after applying the first input signal, the planning horizon is moved forward in time, and the entire planning process is repeated.

Figure 29. Architecture of the planner.

3.2.2. Results

To demonstrate the planner’s capabilities, we set up an overtaking scenario in simulation to test the risk assessment module stand-alone. Here, the ego vehicle predicts the future trajectory of another vehicle, denoted as an object vehicle. The prediction of the object’s trajectory is associated with Gaussian uncertainty in the object’s position, orientation, and velocity. Three circles approximate each actor’s rectangular shapes. For each circle-to-circle pair, the kinematic energy estimates the collision severity. The expected value over all circles then constitutes the risk. As these are intermediate results, the potential field, modelling the road geometry (see Figure 29), is not integrated yet. We simulate three different levels of uncertainty: low, moderate, and high, respectively. The results are depicted in Figure 30.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 30: Overtaking scenario with varying uncertainty (note that the time is only depicted for the high uncertainty case for visibility)

Figure 30 shows that the lower the uncertainty, the closer the ego vehicle is to the object during the overtaking manoeuvre. Also, the velocities vary more strongly for lower uncertainties.

3.2.3. Conclusions

We use a stochastic model predictive controller (SMPC) with a risk metric to balance risk with travel efficiency under uncertainty. In our first simulation study, we find that the SMPC acts increasingly conservative with increasing uncertainty, as desired. As a next step, we will implement the artificial potential field, which includes the road network and perform more extensive analysis of which the results will be provided in Deliverable D2.4 and D3.4.

3.3. Transition of Control

The idea behind this research is to improve the transition of control from automated driving to manual driving by taking into account the state of the driver. The research comprises three topics:

1. Driver state estimation: the following input from the algorithms developed in WP3 are used (see also Figure 31):
 - a. Situational Awareness of the driver ('SA'), which in turn uses the gaze region of the driver (see D3.1 (Muttersbach & Löw, 2024) & D3.2 (Cañas, 2025 (in progress)))
 - b. Driver distraction as received from the WP3 algorithm (see D3.1 and D3.2)
 - c. Mental workload of driver as received from the WP3 algorithm (see D3.1 and D3.2)
 - d. Hands on the steering wheel detection as received from the WP3 algorithm (see D3.1 and D3.2)
2. Decision making for the Transition of Control (see 3.3.2)
3. Perform actions towards the driver through the iHMI (see D3.3).

D2.2 – Active Safety System

Figure 31. Interconnection of algorithms for Transition of Control in Demonstrator 3

3.3.1. Situational Awareness

The situational awareness of the driver as used in AWARE2ALL is probably best defined by (Endsley, 1987) as ‘the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning, and the projection of their status in the near future’. The foreseen algorithm to estimate this Situational Awareness is based on the model called AttenD2.0 by (Ahlström, Georgoulas, & Kircher, 2022), that aims to identify driver distraction. More information on the algorithm will be reported in D3.1 and D3.2.

The basic concept is to track where the driver is looking at using an eye tracking device. Different areas of interest are defined, like e.g. forward roadway, different mirrors, the dashboard, etc. For each of this area a ‘view-buffer’ is defined. A buffer is filling up, when the driver is looking at the associated area of interest and slowly emptying when the driver is not looking at the associated area. The buffers thus represent the current SA of the driver. Next to this, the traffic situation combined with a possible upcoming manoeuvre requires a certain amount of SA. For example, before changing lanes, a driver should be aware of the traffic in the new lane. By matching the current state of the buffers and the required SA for an upcoming manoeuvre, a conclusion on the goodness of the driver SA is made and supportive measures, like e.g. HMI warnings, may be taken.

The estimated SA and required SA are also combined into an SA number that should reflect the overall SA of the driver. This is done per area and a weight per area is added as well, e.g. the front view is weighted more important than the rear view. The weighted results per area are then summed to a single SA number, which is used in the decision making for Transition of Control.

3.3.2. Decision-Making for Transition of Control (Decision TOC)

This research focuses on the development of a cascade fuzzy control system designed to evaluate a driver's readiness to resume control from an autonomous vehicle. This system utilizes multiple inputs, including the criticality of the situation, the driver's awareness level, cognitive load, hands

D2.2 – Active Safety System

on/off status, and the driver's health status. The primary output of this system is a percentage value indicating the driver's preparedness to take control of the vehicle.

The Decision TOC module, shown in Figure 31, combines two sub-modules: Decision-Making and Transition of Control.

Key Components:

1. Inputs:

- Criticality of Situation: Assessing the urgency and severity of the driving scenario.
- Situational Awareness: The output from the SA module, as described in Section 3.3.1, provides information about the driver's attentiveness and focus. It is represented as a percentage ranging from 0% to 100%.
- Cognitive Overload: Evaluating the mental workload on the driver.
- Driver's Health: Considering the physical and mental condition of the driver.
- Hands On/Off Status: Data from steering wheel sensors indicating whether the driver is physically interacting with the vehicle.

2. Outputs from Decision-Making/Inputs for Transition of Control:

The output percentage, rate of readiness and estimated time to full readiness are intended to be fed into the Transition of Control module in the autonomous vehicle system:

- Percentage Readiness: The main output is a percentage value representing the driver's readiness to assume control. This output serves as a crucial parameter for the transition of control module.
- Rate and Direction of Readiness Change: Insights into how the driver's readiness is evolving over time (e.g., improving, deteriorating).
- Estimated Time to High Readiness: A prediction of how long it will take for the driver to reach a state of full readiness, if not already there.

3. Output:

- The Transition of Control module will utilize its inputs to decide when to initiate the transfer of control from the vehicle to the driver.

4. Future Steps:

- Data Set Acquisition: The success of our future steps and research heavily depends on acquiring appropriate data sets for training model that would estimate reaction time
- Estimated Reaction Time: The next phase of our research will involve incorporating an estimation of the driver's reaction time along with the readiness percentage.
- Transition Timing Analysis: This additional metric aims to provide insights into the window of time available for the transition of control module to execute the handover successfully.

In conclusion, our ongoing work focuses on creating an advanced control system that not only assesses driver readiness but also considers the critical factor of transition timing, contributing to the seamless integration of autonomous and manual control in vehicles.

3.4. Adaptive Co-Pilot

This use case showcases real-time interaction at the control level between drivers and highly automated vehicles (HAVs). Strategies will be developed so automation continually assists drivers (instead of replacing them), to improve road safety. In this sense the automated vehicle acts as an adaptive co-pilot that supports the human in the driving task.

Shared control is a concept in automated driving where both the driver and the automated assistance system share control authority, with the distribution of control dynamically shifting based on the driver's state and the state of the road. The system employs haptic feedback, such as tactile sensations or forces, to communicate information to the driver and collaboratively manage control responsibilities. The goal is to optimize safety and performance by adapting the level of automation depending on real-time factors, having a seamless interaction between the human driver and the automated system.

3.4.1. Shared control system

In a first step, before implementing the shared control strategy the shared control system is integrated in a new software environment migrating from a previous solution scheme based on Matlab Simulink. Now the system works in a Linux-based environment with ROS2 nodes. In addition, the solution was dockerized in three modules as shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32. Dockerized solution for shared control system

The first module is CARLA, an open-source automated driving simulator which has the capability to include multiple types of scenarios, generate traffic, and provides an integral and flexible solution for driving simulation environments, which can be managed using a Python API.

The second module is the Simulator, which encompasses all the physical devices of the driving simulator platform. In this case, it is of interest to include the reading and control of the throttle, brake, and steering wheel actuators. With this approach, even if the driving simulator software changes or the vehicle control actuators are replaced with others, the shared control system can keep working with the same scheme.

D2.2 – Active Safety System

The third module is the shared control system, comprised by three main nodes: 1) the MPC node, which handles the lateral and longitudinal control of the vehicle system using a NMPC approach with the help of the ACADO Toolkit C++ software, 2) the planner node, that generates the trajectories to be followed by the MPC node and 3) the simulator manager node, that serves as an interface between the controller and the driving simulator environment.

In addition to these nodes, there is an application to control the weights of the MPC controller in an easy manner, and also a plotter of the references and the predictions of the vehicle system to debug the behaviour of the controller as it can be seen in **Figure 33**.

Figure 33. Graphic user interface for adjusting the NMPC weight and plotter to debug the MPC controller

The integration of the multiple nodes and modules is shown in **Figure 34** and **Figure 35**.

Figure 34. Integration of Actuators, Shared Control and CARLA modules using dockers and ROS2.

Figure 35. Real data printing when MPC is operative for nodes simulator, MPC and planner.

3.4.2. Shared control strategy

For the adaptive co-pilot use case, a haptic shared control strategy is designed to couple the commands of the driver and the vehicle automation for both longitudinal and lateral control of the vehicle. This strategy is well known in the literature as uncoupled shared control, which works under the following principles (see e.g. (Marcano, Díaz, Pérez, & Irigoyen, 2020), (Koerten, Abbink, & Zgonnikov, 2024) and (Perozzi, Rath, Sentouth, Floris, & Popieul, 2021)).

- The vehicle control mechanism is uncoupled of the vehicle system. This is also known as drive-by-wire mechanism.
- The vehicle system follows the driver command under normal/safe circumstances. In this case, the vehicle systems act as a regular mechanical coupled system (i.e., the system responds congruently to the driver actions).

D2.2 – Active Safety System

- The vehicle system is able to override, complement or attenuate driver actions in order to improve performance, preserve safety or even keep some comfort expectations.

This approach is applied for both the longitudinal and lateral control of the vehicle system.

- **Longitudinal control:** It's based on the MPC controller with triple integrator of acceleration, speed, and position, with the minimization of the vehicle speed function $\|v - v_{ref}\|_{w_v}^2$ along the prediction horizon (where v is the ego vehicle speed, and v_{ref} the controlled reference speed) With this function the MPC acts as a longitudinal speed controller. To add the uncoupled shared control strategy a new term is added to the minimization function, where the control acceleration value for the speed controller is matched with the driver throttle command $\|a_{mpc} - a_{driver}\|_{w_a}^2$ (where a_{mpc} is the acceleration as commanded by the MPC controller, and a_{driver} , the acceleration as commanded by the driver). In this sense the driver commands behave as a dynamic reference for the control output of the MPC. Therefore, the balance between the weights of the two function terms (w_v and w_a) will determine whether the systems is controlled more by automation or by the driver, such that if $w_v \gg w_a$ the system will act as a full automated speed controller, while on the contrary it will act as a full manually driven vehicle. The balance of such weight will depend on the applications which are: 1) speed limit controller, and 2) adaptive cruise control. On the other hand, the driver feeling at the throttle pedal is applied separately with a proportional force to $a_{mpc} - a_{driver}$. This will be one of the benefits of the haptic throttle pedal, to communicate to the driver through force feedback the difference between his action and the optimal pedal position.
- **Lateral control:** It's based on the NMPC approach using a dynamic bicycle model and minimizing the lateral and angular error of the vehicle against the desired trajectory. In this case the minimization function is $\|e_y\|_{w_{ey}}^2 + \|e_\psi\|_{w_{e\psi}}^2$ that configures the NMPC to act as a trajectory tracking controller (where e_y is the lateral position error with respect to the trajectory, e_ψ the angular error with respect to the trajectory and $(w_{ey}, w_{e\psi})$ their respective weights) The output of the controller is the torque command to manage the steering wheel of the vehicle such that its force can be modulated to interact appropriately with the driver. In order to include the uncoupled strategy, a new term is added to include the driver command at the steering wheel $\|\delta_{mpc} - \delta_{driver}\|_{w_\delta}^2$ (with δ_{mpc} the steering angle as commanded by the MPC controller and δ_{driver} the steering angle as commanded by the driver). In this case the balance between $(w_{ey}, w_{e\psi})$ and w_δ will determine the behaviour of the system. In this type of control, the weights are modified in terms of a risk evaluation of the environment (e.g., if there is risk of departing the lane, the weights of the tracking controller increase). The haptic feedback felt in the hands by the driver will be proportional to $\delta_{mpc} - \delta_{driver}$.

The longitudinal and lateral control of the vehicle will be verified in Task 2.4, where the performance of the controllers will be assessed. As for the longitudinal control, we will focus on the ability of the haptic pedals to help drivers keep speed limits and keep a safe distance from the leading vehicle. On the other hand, with lateral control, the focus lies on the ability of the controller to follow the driver's command during safe driving and to overcome the unsafe actions of the drivers helping to keep them within the driving lane.

4. Conclusions

This deliverable reports the results of Task 2.2 of the AWARE2ALL project. The results are twofold:

1. Build / update the required physical hardware for the involved Demonstrator 2 and Demonstrator 3
2. Develop algorithms to further research and developments on the topic of Active Safety.

Following has been developed in task 2.2:

Demonstrator 2:

- The Robobus from PiX³, is an autonomous shuttle platform designed to operate without a human driver, utilizing sensors, cameras and AI technology to navigate roads and transport passengers safely. Additionally, to support the localization system, a LiDAR and algorithms for roadside detection of the shuttle were setup and programmed as well as I2V communication from the roadside to the shuttle.
- Prediction of passenger body motion that is based on acceleration values resulting from pre-crash simulations. Using MADYMO, different human models (active and passive), placed in various standing poses (facing forward and facing sideways) and configurations (two hands on the vehicle grab handle, one or none) and sitting positions rearwards and forward facing have been evaluated to find limiting accelerations for safe manoeuvring.
- The result of the passenger body motion is input for the design of pre-crash trajectories. An algorithm has been designed to take the limiting accelerations into account for an optimal upcoming pre-crash scenario.
- Improved operational reliability through deployment strategies for fault-tolerant strategies in case of system positioning sensor failure including fail-operational functionalities, and emergency situations, such as AEB, evasive manoeuvring or safe/comfortable stops. Following scenarios have been implemented:
 - o degradation of the GNSS signal: an algorithm using I2V localisation information is designed as a fault-tolerant strategy.
 - o when additionally to the GNSS degradation also the LiDAR-based positioning algorithm fails then an algorithm based on I2V localisation is activated.
- Decision making and control of the shuttle: these algorithms control the motion of the shuttle either in normal operation or in one of the pre-crash scenarios connected to this Demonstrator.

Demonstrator 3:

- The main physical system is the hybrid driving simulator from partner SYSX. It is based on a physical cockpit and a virtual environment to run the (human factors) experiments.
- Risk field estimation and safety relevant trajectory adaptation and control modules are researched and applied to increase the lateral acceleration range for the evasive manoeuvre including the acceptance of lane change manoeuvre.

³ PiX shuttles: <https://www.pixmoving.com/>

D2.2 – Active Safety System

- An algorithm has been designed to estimate the readiness of the driver to resume control after automated driving. This algorithm, referred to as Decision Making, takes as input the results of specific algorithms designed in WP3, such as Situation Awareness estimation, hands on/off detection, driver health, cognitive workload, and criticality of the situation. The result of the Decision Making algorithm is used to shape the transition of control from automated driving to manual driving.
- Adaptive support for drivers, depending on the driving context, such as driver state (e.g. from the Decision Making algorithm) or risk estimation, by means of steering system and haptic pedals. This comprises a haptic shared control algorithm, supported by a drive-by-wire setup with a haptic steering wheel and haptic accelerator pedal. All parts were implemented in a driving simulator of partner TEC (parallel part of Demonstrator 3).

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